

NFDI4Objects
National Library of
Science, Technology
& Linked Open Data

Beyond Digital Boundaries

Linked Open Data and Wikidata with OG(H)AM and Holy Wells

Florian Thiery M.Sc.

UK-Ireland DH Association Annual Event 2025 | 17-18 Jun 2025 |

Glasgow | Scotland @ United Kingdom | 18/06/2025

Session 5B. Cultural Heritage beyond boundaries

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There is a lot of chaos in the FAIR Ogham data forest ...

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... while excavating and publishing research data in the LOD cloud ...

... using Linked Open Data techniques!

F A I R

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

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via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data (LOD) is the method of choice for linking data and FAIRification ...

... to expand the Linked Open Data Cloud.

This project focuses on cataloguing and linking data related to Irish Ogham stones, ancient inscribed monoliths that provide essential insights into early medieval language, culture, and identity in Ireland.

By using Linked Open Data and platforms like Wikidata, the project seeks to enhance the accessibility and cross-referencing of these inscriptions across archaeological and linguistic research. Wikimedia Germany funded it in 2020/21.

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Me & my Dad in Ireland looking for Ogham Stones

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

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The Linked Open Ogham LOD / Wikidata Workflow

Linked Open Ogham Stones

... creating Linked Open Data

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153.—(No. VI).

At Chute Hall. Grit, 3' 4" × 1' 0" × 0' 7". Inscription on two diagonally opposed angles, up-down.

CCICAMINI MAQQI CATTINI

Of 4I, all but I¹ is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of CATTINI and the following A. The doubled initial C does not appear to be anything more than an engraver's freak: it would be a mistake to separate CCI from the rest of the names and to equate it to the always enclitic KOI. We shall see a similar beginning at Camp (177).

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.1492

Example: CIIC 153 Ballinrannig VI

Extract from the Linked Open Ogham Ontology

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153_Ballinrannig_VI

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Ogham in 3D

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CIIC 153, Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry
Site Type
Description
Site
Monument
Text
Transliteration
Translation
Commentary
Locations
Found
Original
Last Recorded
History of Recording
References
Websites and Online Databases

CIIC 153, Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry
Site Type
Description
Site
Monument
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Commentary
Locations
Found
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Last Recorded
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CIIC 153, Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry
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Transliteration
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References
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Download Epidoc | URI https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153_Ballinrannig_VI

National Monuments Service Record Number: KE942-057011.

Site Type
Burial ground and probable ecclesiastical site

Description
Site
"Cillvickillane/Cill Mhíic *Líleáir*: A large, grass-grown, sandy knoll, crowned by a single ogham stone, is located at the base of a small promontory on the S shore of Smervick Harbour. It was here that a storm at the end of the 18th century exposed 7 ogham stones, a possible fragment of an ogham stone, a cross-inscribed stone, a number of graves and quantities of bone, and the ruins of several houses (Windele 1838, 145; Chatterton 1839, 194). Windele's sketch of the site shows the ogham stones set out in a rough semi-circle on top of the mound with a slab-lined grave positioned nearby. Chatterton describes the houses as being beyond the mound nearer the sea. Windele interpreted these as the remains of an ancient village, but it has also been suggested that one of the structures, roughly 20 feet x 12 feet (6 x 3.7m), was a church (Curran no. 21). Lord Ventry removed 6 of the ogham stones from the site in the mid-19th century; nos. 1 to 4 now line the driveway to Burnham House/Colaiste Íde, between Dingle and Ventry, and nos. 5 and 6 are preserved in the grounds of Chute Hall near Tralee. Only no 7 is still preserved on the original site" (Cuppige 1986, 250-2).

Monument
"Grif, 1.02m x 0.30m x 0.18m (Converted from Macalister 1945, 149). Some damage evident at the top of the stone.

Text
The inscription is up-top-down, 'on two diagonally opposed angles... Of 4l [MAQO]l, but 1l is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A' (Macalister 1945, 149). It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorated CCICAMINI and the following formula word MAQO (represented by 'vac' below). This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also CIIC 119 Monastagart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by Mollat (2011, 290).

Transliteration
CCICAMINivac: MAQOQI] CJA]TTINI

Translation
of C? son of Caine?

Commentary
• The father's name CATTINI (later Catne) likewise occurs as the father's name in an inscription found at Ballintaggart (CIIC 157), a site also located in Corca Dhubhíne territory.

Locations
Found
Exposed by a storm at the end of the 18th century, along with 6 other ogham stones (Cuppige 1986, 250), in the townland of Ballinrannig and barony of Corkaguiney. (GPS coordinates -10.388106, 52.178511)

Original
Find location probably original site

Last Recorded
In the mid 19th century this stone and CIIC 153 were moved by Lord Ventry to Chute Hall, near Tralee, where they remain today. The present location of this stone may be accessed via the National Monuments Service Historic Environment viewer on www.archaeology.ie (GPS coordinates-9.642423, 52.275855)

History of Recording
First recognised in 1782 by Fitham and recorded by Vallancey (1804) in *Collectanea de Rebus Hibernicis* 6, 226 (Macalister 1945, 144). This stone was recorded for the Ogham in 3D project in 2017 by Helena Zacharias, a participant on the Corca Dhubhíne 3d project, using Structure from Motion 3d technology.

References
• Bennett I. and Uí Shéithigh B. (1995). *Ogham Stones of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 7-8.
• Cuppige, J. et al (1986). *Archaeological Survey of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 250-2.
• Macalister, R.A.S. (1945). *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, pp 144, 149.
• McManus, D. (1991). *A guide to ogham: Maynooth Monographs* 4, p. 108.

Websites and Online Databases
• Corca Dhubhíne 3d: www.corcadhubhine3d.ie
• www.archaeology.ie

Example: CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI (Ogham @ 3D Repository)

```
<div type="description" n="text">
  <head>Text</head>
  <p>The inscription is up-top-down, <q>on two diagonally opposed angles...
    Of 4I [MAQQI], all but I1 is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A</q> (<ref type="bibliog" target="#MAC1945">
      <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
        >149</biblScope></bibl></ref>. It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorate
    This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also <ref
      target="search.php?ciic=118"
    >CIIC 118</ref> Monataggart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by <ref
      type="bibliog" target="#MOF2011"><bibl><author>Moffat</author> (<date
        when="2011">2011</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
        >290</biblScope></bibl></ref>.
  </p>
</div>
```


Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

```
<div type="edition" xml:lang="ga">
  <head xml:lang="en">Transliteration</head>
  <ab>
    <persName><w lemma="CCICAMINI">CCICAMINI</w></persName><space></space>
    <w lemma="MAQI" type="formula">MAQ/Q<supplied reason="lost">/I</supplied></w>
    <persName><w lemma="CATTINI">C<supplied reason="lost">A</supplied>TTINI</w></persName>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="translation" xml:lang="en">
  <head>Translation</head>
  <ab><q>of C? son of Caitne</q></ab>
</div>
```


Example: CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI (as TEI/EpiDoc)

By **Katherine Forsyth**, OG(H)AM UK Principal Investigator

Any of you participating in the 'Dry January' challenge will, I hope, forgive this month's featured ogham. It comes courtesy of a microbrewery on the Isle of Gigha which declares itself 'dedicated to crafting unique, small-batch beers that capture the essence of this stunning Hebridean island. ... every pint is a love letter to this special place.' That letter is written in the ogham alphabet, of course!

Gigha Brewery are proud of the island's wonderful ogham pillar which we were delighted to visit and record back in 2022 when we acquired these bottles – for purely scientific purposes 🧐. There is a separate section on their [website](#) dedicated to ogham – the only brewery in the world to be so distinguished – and the script also features on their product labels. Ogham is not so easy on a smooth, round bottle (though there are ways!), and they employ a drawn-in stem-line, but the script is otherwise classic. They even use the first forid (X) in its oldest value: /k/ to represent the first letter of their top-brewed 'Kölsch'-style beer.

As you can see, the ogham is used to represent the English names of their beers and, as often happens with modern use of ogham mediated via the Web, the letters are rather widely spaced. They could all be slightly closer together, especially in G-O-L-D-E-N A-L-E where there are no two successive letters from the same *aicme* (group). So, there is no room for confusion – exactly as the script was planned to ensure.

Og(h)am of the Month Jan 2025: S-ARL-001 (CIIC 506 | GIGHA/1)

Ogham as part of the local heritage and brewery identity

Ogham

What is Ogham

What is Ogham?

Other than on your bottle design, Ogham is an Early Medieval alphabet used primarily to write the early Irish language, and later the Old Irish language. There are roughly 400 surviving orthographic inscriptions on stone monuments throughout Ireland and western Britain, the bulk of which are in southern Munster.

Corpus

Monumental ogham inscriptions are found in Ireland and Wales, with a few additional specimens found in south-west England (Devon and Cornwall), the Isle of Man, and Scotland, including Shetland and a single example from Schiester in England. They were mainly employed as territorial markers and memorials (grave stones). The stone commemorating Vortiporus, a 5th-century king of Dyfed (originally located in Cymdeirion), is the only ogham stone inscription that bears the name of an identifiable individual. The language of the inscriptions is predominantly Primitive Irish, the few inscriptions in Scotland, such as the Lunning Stone, record fragments of what is probably the Pictish language.

The more ancient examples are standing stones, where the script was carved into the edge (drom or foobar) of the stone, which formed the stemline against which individual characters are cut. The text of these "orthodox Ogham" inscriptions is read beginning from the bottom left-hand side of a stone, continuing upwards along the edge across the top and down the right-hand side (in the case of long inscriptions). Roughly 300 inscriptions are known in total (a number, incidentally, very close to the number of known inscriptions in the contemporary Etruscan alphabet) of which the heaviest concentration by far is found in the

The Ogham stone on Gigha

Situated just west of the ruins of Kishbatten Church, is the Cnoc A'Chomaidh (hill of the Pile) on which stands the inscribed Ogham Stone. This pillar is square in section, standing five feet nine inches from the ground and measuring 3 feet 3 inches in circumference at the top. Throughout the years it has received a fair amount of knocks, and the weathering on the exposed side has made it difficult to get a perfect transcription of the original sculpturing. However Professor R. A. S. Macalister has given the reading as 'NOLLA MACH CROAIB' - 'NOLLA SON OF CROAIB' - and holds the opinion that it is a Scottish inscription cut under Pictish influence. Although there are other suggestions as to the meaning of the words, it is a grave-stone with the conventional type of inscription giving the name of the deceased and that of his father, and probably dates from the earliest settlements of the Scots in Galloway.

Gighas Ogham Stone

Following the launch of trove.scot in February 2025 we are now planning the retiral of some of our web services. Canmore will be switched off on 24th June 2025. Information about the closure can be found on the HES website: [Retiral of HES web services](#) | [Historic Environment Scotland](#)

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Ogham Stone located on the Isle of Gigha / Giogha

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Following the launch of [trove.scot](#) in February 2025 we are now planning the retrial of some of our webservices. Canmore will be switched off on 24th June 2025. Information about the closure can be found on the HES website: [Retrial of HES web services](#) | [Historic Environment Scotland](#)

Gigha, Cnoc Na Carraigh

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- [MyCanmore Text](#)

Ogham Inscribed Stone (Early Medieval), Standing Stone (Prehistoric)

Site Name Gigha, Cnoc Na Carraigh
Classification Ogham Inscribed Stone (Early Medieval), Standing Stone (Prehistoric)
Canmore ID 38529
Site Number NR64NW 2
NGR NR 6426 4817
Datum OSGB36 - NGR
Permalink <http://canmore.org.uk/site/38529>

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1:10,000 Quarter Sheet NR 64 NW	2	OS No.	STRATHCLYDE	New 004 COUNTY	ARGYLL	TYPE 2 3 4	V Page 1
NGR NR 6426 4817	CE	Dist No.	ARGYLL & BUTE	DIST PAR	GIGHA & CARA	FORM STANDING STRUCTURE	
Definition Record No. Ref.						PERIOD Incomplete	
				SCHEDULED	STATUS 0 or 1000		
SITE NAME AND MAIN FEATURES CNOC NA CARRAIGH, GIGHA Ogham-inscribed Standing Stone (NR 64274818) Standing Stone (NR).						OS No only Inscribed Stone (NR) (Ogham) [NAT]	
A four-sided granite pillar 1.7m high bearing an Ogham inscription on its SW edge; the sides of the pillar measure 0.25m to 0.31m at the base and 0.20m to 0.25m at the top. What appears to have been the same stone was described by Martin in the late 17th century as being about 3m high, and although his estimate is probably exaggerated it is known that a piece of the top was broken off when the stone was knocked down about 1845. Some twenty years later it fell again and on this occasion it was not re-erected precisely on the original site, but close to it (b).						1. OS 6" 1924 2. ECAHM Kintyre 1971 96-7 No 244 Illust. Visited 1966 a. A Description of the Western Islands of Scotland 1934 263 (M Martin) b. JRS&I 31 1901 18ff	
The Ogham inscription is defaced by a series of holes on the base-line, but Professor K H Jackson suggests, very tentatively, that it may have read 'the son of Coicéille'						= 3 Rlys 1901 = Bibm. 26627 S614 S082	

48 495 .td

<https://canmore.org.uk/collection/2415903>

The Ogham Stone is well-documented in CANMORE

via <https://github.com/guariento/og-h-am/blob/main/XML/S-ARL/S-ARL-001.xml>

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<publicationStmt>
  <authority>OG(H)AM</authority>
  <idno type="filename">S-ARL-001</idno>
  <idno type="CIIC">506</idno>
  <idno type="CISP">GIGHA/1</idno>
  <availability>
    <licence target="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License</licence>
  </availability>
</publicationStmt>

<sourceDesc>
  <msDesc>
    <msIdentifier>
      <country>Scotland</country>
      <repository/>
      <idno type="invNo"/>
    </msIdentifier>
    <msContents>
      <msItem>
        <textLang mainLang="sga-0gam" cert="low">Possibly old Irish written in ogham script</textLang>
      </msItem>
    </msContents>
    <physDesc>
      <objectDesc>
        <supportDesc>
          <support><ref target="https://www.trove.scot/place/38529">Trove</ref> <idno type="Trove">38529</idno></support>
          <material type="stone">Granite</material>
          <objectType key="monument">Pillar</objectType>
          <dimensions unit="m">
            <height>1.7</height>
            <width>0.25 at base, 0.20 at the top</width>
            <depth>0.31 at base, 0.23 at the top</depth>
          </dimensions>
        </supportDesc>
        <condition>A tall, square-shaped pillar, it <q>is unclear whether the monument is a re-used pre-historic standing stone or a pillar specially erected for the bearing of the inscription</q> (Forsyth 1996, 289). <q>The stone has fallen and been re-erected at least twice</q>; the first time it was intentionally toppled by some young men while the second fall was as a result of quarrying near the base on one side of the stone (ibid. 288-289). There is general weathering with <q>a series of four large, shallow, unevenly spaced chunks missing from the ogham-bearing aris</q> (ibid. 290). The ogham inscription <q>which is worn and in bad condition, is defaced by series of spalls - the aris</q> (ibid. 290). The portion of the inscription <q>nearest the ground is the most badly worn and the most disputed</q> (ibid. 291).
        </condition>
      </objectDesc>
      <layoutDesc>
        <layout style="vertical" rend="arris_up">The ogham inscription is on the north west edge of the four-sided pillar stone and reads upwards from the bottom.
      </layoutDesc>
      <objectDesc>
        <handDesc>
          <handNote>There is a wide range of published interpretations of the ogham that along with its general poor condition make a definitive reading difficult. On the same grounds, it is difficult to make definitive statements about its carving technique. <q>As they now survive, the strokes are finger-scale and with a U-section, where it can be measured with any certainty the length of h-acute strokes is about <math>40\text{--}60\text{mm}</math></q> (Forsyth 1996, 291). The gaps between the letters most likely contained vowel notches now lost. Forsyth (ibid. 295) describes the ogham inscription as <q>ogham with no drawn stem-line and vowels which are little more than nicks - the 'text-book' form of the script</q>.
        </handNote>
      </handDesc>
    </physDesc>
    <history>
      <origin>
        <origPlace>
          <placeName type="parish">Gigha and Cara</placeName>, <placeName type="county">Argyll</placeName>, <placeName type="country">Scotland</placeName>
          <geo>55.669722, -5.750278</geo>
          <note>National Grid Reference: NR 6426 4817</note>
        </origPlace>
        <origDate/>
      </origin>
      <provenance type="found" when="1873">Formerly the middle stone of a straight alignment of three stones known locally as the 'Clocks of Gigha'. The ogham stone is located on a hillock, <placeName>Cnoc na Carraigh ('hill of the rock')</placeName>, about 90 m NW of the ruined chapel of Kilchattan on the island of <placeName>Gigha</placeName>. Although the stone has been noted since <date>1695</date>, the inscription was not noticed until <date>1873</date>.
      </provenance>
      <provenance type="observed" when="2022-09-14">Visited and recorded in situ in 2022.
      </provenance>
    </history>
  </msDesc>
</sourceDesc>
```

E22

E25

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

```

<text>
<body>
<div type="edition" subtype="ogham" xml:space="preserve" xml:lang="sga-Ogam" cert="low" resp="#XS">
  <ab>
    <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"><gap reason="lost" quantity="6" unit="character"/><unclear cert="low"/></unclear><gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/></unclear cert="low"/></unclear><gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="edition" subtype="transliteration" xml:lang="sga-Ogam" cert="low" xml:space="preserve" resp="#KF">
  <ab>
    <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"><gap reason="lost" quantity="6" unit="character"/><unclear cert="low">MA</unclear>Q<gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/>C<unclear cert="low">OGIN</unclear><gap reason="lost" extent="unknown" unit="character"/>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="apparatus">
  <listApp>
    <app n="1">
      <note>As Forsyth notes <q>The first six letters are extremely doubtful</q>. For the portion of the inscription closest to the ground, the indentations of strokes <q>can be clearly felt on the arbris, but the lines are too indistinct to interpret</q> (1996, 292). From the seventh character onwards the carving is clearer and there is greater agreement amongst previous editors (ibid. 293).</note>
    </app>
    <app n="2">
      <note>Rhys (1899) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1899">
        MAQICAGILEB
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="3">
      <note>Rhys (1901, 18-23) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="RHY1901">
        OGMMA MAQI TIGERNI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="4">
      <note>Macalister (1902) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="MAC1902">
        VICULA MAQ COMGINI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <app n="5">
      <note>Macalister (1945, 484) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="MAC1945">
        VICULA MAQ CUGINI
      </rdg>
    </app>
    <!--<app n="6">
      <note>Diack (1926) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="DIA1926">
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
        VIDDOOSAMO QICOGINI
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    <!--<app n="7">
      <note>Jackson (1971, 96-97) read:</note>
      <rdg resp="JAC1971">
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:up"/>
        H\.\JMAQT/cAGII/bb
      </rdg>
      </app> Reference not in Zotero -->
    </listApp>
  </div>
  <div type="translation">
    <p>According to Forsyth (1996, 297), Jackson offered <q>a very hypothetical</q> interpretation: the son of <persName>Coicéile</persName> (see <ref target="https://canmore.org.uk/event/695592">Canmore</ref>).</p>
  </div>
  <div type="commentary">
    <p><q>If the letters before the M are not admitted then the formula 'MAQ-X' is likely, either as 'the son of X', or more likely, as a compound name with first element MAQ (Forsyth 1996, 296)</q> However, Forsyth maintains that there is sufficient evidence for the existence of some ogham carvings before the letter M which consequently implies that Gigha 1 conforms to the Irish formula 'X son of Y'.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 297) also rejects Macalister's suggestion for VICULA as <foreign xml:lang="sga">Fiacal</foreign> meaning 'tooth' on the grounds that <q>OIr ia is from earlier e, both long and short i remained as i</q>. Meanwhile the second name COMGINI is interpreted by Macalister as OIR <persName xml:lang="sga">Coemgen</persName>, which Forsyth comments is a <q>widespread and well-known male name (<foreign xml:lang="sga">Crefi target="https://doi.org/10.7550/Coem</ref></foreign> + <foreign xml:lang="sga">gen</foreign> 'Fair born' (Uhllich 1993:2071)), found variously spelled, including <persName xml:lang="ga">Comganiz</persName></q>.
    <p>Forsyth (1996, 296) is in favor of considering this example as one of the earliest oghams in Scotland due to the fact that comparable scripts are ubiquitous in Ireland. Moreover, the stone's size and shape, and the positioning of the inscriptions' lettering and proportion of its strokes which is, as she notes <q>closest of all the Scottish examples to the Southern Irish norm</q> (ibid., 297).
  </div>

```

TX1

TX6

Gigha Stone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

By **Megan Kasten**, OG(H)AM UK Postdoctoral Researcher

In May, Megan and Katherine 3D recorded ogham stones in Aberdeenshire, including this month's Ogham of the Month: Logie Elphinstone (S-ABD-002; [Canmore ID 1855](#)). Logie Elphinstone 2 is a pillar of an unusually pointed shape and measures 1.37m high and 0.46m wide. Like several of the Aberdeenshire ogham stones, it appears to be a reused prehistoric standing stone, formerly part of a stone circle (it was originally discovered with at least two other Pictish symbol stones, a fourth having been destroyed when reused in a kiln).

3D Model of Logie Elphinstone 2 using Meshlab's Radiance Scaling.

The stone is incised with two layers of Pictish symbols (the partially erased double-disc is visible under the clearer pair of Crescent-and-V-rod and Double-disc-and-Z-rod). Above the symbols are five ogham letters carved on a circular stem-line. The Buckquoy spindle whorl ([March 2022's Ogham of the month](#)) and the amber bead from Ennis (I-[CLA-003](#)) also have stemlines which are circular loops, but in those cases the objects are circular: this is a unique example on flat stone. It may be intended to recall the ogham-inscribed wooden hoops, or withies, referred to in Early Irish sagas as being left on pillar stones as a warning to passersby. The letters can be read QFTQU in a circle, or NFINU if reading in the other direction, but it is not clear in either case where one is meant to start. Perhaps the text is deliberately cryptic, like some of the fictional oghams described in the sagas.

Og(h)am of the Month Jun 2022: S-ABD-002 (LPHIN/1)

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Following the launch of [trove.scot](#) in February 2025 we are now planning the retirement of some of our webservices. Canmore will be switched off on 24th June 2025. Information about the closure can be found on the HES website: [Retiral of HES web services](#) | [Historic Environment Scotland](#)

Map

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Logie Elphinstone

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- [Activities](#)
- [References](#)
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- [MyCanmore Text](#)

Ogham Inscribed Stone (Pictish), Pictish Symbol Stone (Pictish)

Site Name Logie Elphinstone
Classification Ogham Inscribed Stone (Pictish), Pictish Symbol Stone (Pictish)
Alternative Name(s) Logie House Policies; Logie Elphinstone No. 2, Moor Of Carden
Canmore ID 18855
Site Number NJ72NW 7.02
NGR NJ 7034 2588
Datum OSG836 - NGR
Permalink <http://canmore.org.uk/site/18855>

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[Correction](#)
[Favourite](#)

Logie Elphinstone in CANMORE

Logie Elphinstone in Sketchfab

```
<publicationStmnt>
  <authority>OG(H)AM</authority>
  <idno type="filename">S-ABD-002</idno>
  <idno type="CIIC"/>
  <idno type="CIISP" corresp="https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/lphin_1.html">LPHIN/1</idno>
  <availability>
    <licence target="https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License</licence>
  </availability>
</publicationStmnt>

<sourceDesc>
  <msDesc>
    <msIdentifier>
      <country>Scotland</country>
      <repository>
        <idno type="invNo"/>
      </msIdentifier>
    <msContent>
      <msItem>
        <textLang mainLang="und-Ogam">Undetermined language written in ogham script</textLang>
      </msItem>
    </msContent>
  </msDesc>
  <physDesc>
    <objectDesc>
      <supportDesc>
        <support>
          <ref target="https://www.trove.scot/place/18855">Trove</ref> <idno type="Trove">18855</idno></support>
          <material type="stone">Granite</material>
          <objectType key="monument">Class I Pictish symbol stone</objectType>
          <dimensions unit="m">
            <height>1.37</height>
            <width>0.76</width>
            <depth>0.45</depth>
          </dimensions>
          <desc type="decoration">The lower two-thirds are occupied by a pair of Pictish symbols, a <rs type="decoration" key="PictishSymbol"> crescent-and-V-rod over double-disc-and-Z-rod</rs> (Forsyth 1996, 390). The carving of the symbols is <q>broader, deeper, and smoother</q> than the ogham carving, <q>but this may reflect nothing more than the larger scale of the former</q> (ibid. 391)</desc>
        </support>
        <condition>The monument is likely a prehistoric standing stone (blue granite) which was reused for the carving of Pictish symbols and an ogham inscription both of which are intact and well-preserved.</condition>
      </supportDesc>
      <layoutDesc>
        <layout type="other" rend="stamline_circular">The ogham inscription is cut on a circular stem in the middle of the top third of the pointed pillar. The reading starts from the 10 o'clock position, as this is where the largest gap is located, and continues clockwise (Forsyth 1996, 394).</layout>
      </layoutDesc>
    </objectDesc>
    <handDesc>
      <handNote>The ogham inscription and symbols were <rs type="execution" key="pocked" ref="https://www.eagle-network.eu/voc/writing/10d/11.html"> pocked and rubbed</rs> smooth, a technique that is typical of Pictish Class I carvings (Forsyth 1996, 391). Strokes are generally evenly spaced and there are generous gaps between letters, though it is important to keep in mind the possibility of distortion due to the circular stem (ibid. 396). The number of strokes per letter is accepted as: 5, 3, 3, 3, 5, 3.
      <height>The shortest letter strokes are 3cm long, the longest are 7cm, and the remainder vary between 4 and 6cm (ibid. 393).</height>
    </handNote>
  </handDesc>
  </physDesc>
  <history>
    <origin>
      <origPlace><placeName type="parish">Chapel Of Garioch</placeName>, <placeName type="county">Aberdeenshire</placeName>, <placeName type="country">Scotland</placeName>
      <geo>57.322500, -2.494167</geo>
      <note>National Grid Reference: NJ 7034 2588</note></origPlace>
      <origdate>
    </origin>
    <provenance type="found" when="1856">First mentioned by J Stuart in <date>1856</date>. This was one of four stones found lying on the ground on the Moor of Carden to the west of Logie Elphinstone House in or prior to about 1821. At that time the moor was planted and three of the stones were built into the enclosing wall, while the fourth (which is not known certainly to have been carved) was used as a floor slab in a kiln and <q>split by the heat and destroyed</q> (Stuart 1856, 4). The three symbol stones were subsequently removed from the wall and erected in the house grounds (Forsyth 1996, 385).
    </provenance>
    <provenance type="observed" when="2022-05-18">Recorded on the grounds of <placeName>Logie Elphinstone House</placeName>, to the west of the house at NJ 7033 2588, on <date>May 18th 2022</date>.
    </provenance>
  </history>
</msDesc>
</sourceDesc>
```

E22

E25

Logie Elphinstone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

```
<text>
  <body>
    <div type="edition" subtype="ogham" xml:lang="und-0gam" xml:space="preserve" resp="#LH">
      <ab>
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:clockwise"/>_+_
      </ab>
    </div>
    <div type="edition" subtype="transliteration" xml:lang="und-0gam" xml:space="preserve" resp="#LH">
      <ab>
        <lb n="1" style="text-direction:clockwise"/>QFTQU TX1
      </ab>
    </div>
    <div type="apparatus">
      <listApp>
        <app n="1">
          <note>According to Forsyth (1996, 398), the lack of vowels <q>strongly suggests that the sequence is either encoded, or has no linguistic significance</q>.</note>
        </app>
        <app n="2">
          <note>There are two <q>clearly artificial</q> scores outside the stem beyond the first and third strokes of the second letter which might be intended as punctuation marks <q>added to differentiate group 2 from the strokes on either side</q> (Forsyth 1996, 395).</note> TX6
        </app>
      </listApp>
    </div>
    <div type="translation">
      <p>Logie is the shortest complete monumental ogham text in Scotland and as such cannot be readily interpreted (Forsyth 1996, 398). </p>
    </div>
    <div type="commentary">
      <p>The placement of the symbols suggests that the ogham was accounted for in the original design which further implies that the ogham relates to the same phase as the symbols, though it cannot be definitively proved. The stone is a palimpsest as there are visible remains of a partially-erased double-disc and Z-rod under the symbols; however, the overall layout strongly supports the assumption that the ogham relates to the second phase (Forsyth 1996, 391-2).</p>
    </div>
    <div type="bibliography">
      <listBibl>
        <bibl><ptr target="FOR1996"/>
          <citedRange>385-401</citedRange>
        </bibl>
        <bibl><ptr target="STU1856"/>
          <citedRange>4</citedRange>
        </bibl>
      </listBibl>
    </div>
  </body>
</text>
```

Logie Elphinstone as TEI/EpiDoc ⇒ CIDOC-CRM and LOD?

Ogham Stones in Wikidata

... using the hugest Knowledge Hub

Stones from
Scotland
Wales
England
Isle of Man
have to be integrated

CIIC 178

- Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head
- OSM: node/5145413640
- Wikidata: Q70892682
- O3d: 178._Coumeenole
- SMR: KE052-059002-

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 178 (5145413640)

Version #8

added historic site #NationalMonuments

Bearbeitet vor .weniger.als.einer.Minute von fthierygo

Änderungssatz #133566233

Standort: 52,1102476, -10,4731913

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	ERC MAQI MAQI- ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
moved	no
name	CIIC 178
project	ogham.link
ref:ismr	KE052-059002-
source	survey
wikidata	Q70892682
wikimedia_commons	File:Coumeenolele_O gham_Stone_(Dunmore Head).jpg

↑ Ogham in 3D Project, DIAS,
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry (Q126503090)

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone, Co. Kerry [edit](#)

Coumeenole Stone

in more languages
[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	–	
English	Ogham Stone Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head, Co. Kerry	Ogham Stone, Co. Kerry	Coumeenole Stone
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	 ogham stone edit
	0 references + add reference
	 Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit
	0 references + add reference
	 archaeological artefact edit
	0 references + add reference
	+ add value

part of	 WikiProject OghamStones edit
	0 references + add reference
	 Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit
	0 references + add reference
	+ add value

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126503090>

image
[edit](#)

Coumeenole Ogham Stone (Dunmore Head).jpg
960 × 1,280, 122 KB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

image
[edit](#)

County Kerry - Coumeenole Stone - 20180915184947.jpg
4,098 × 3,072, 9.78 MB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

image
[edit](#)

Coumeenole Ogham Stone (Dunmore Head) 20220827 1.jpg
4,032 × 1,908, 3.85 MB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

image
[edit](#)

Coumeenole Ogham Stone (Dunmore Head) 20220827 2.jpg
4,032 × 1,908, 2.94 MB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

image
[edit](#)

Coumeenole Ogham Stone (Dunmore Head) 20220827 3.jpg
1,908 × 2,848, 1.35 MB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

image
[edit](#)

Coumeenole Ogham Stone (Dunmore Head) 20220827 4.jpg
4,032 × 1,908, 3.8 MB

0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

country
[edit](#)

Ireland [edit](#)

0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

located in the administrative territorial entity
[edit](#)

County Kerry [edit](#)

0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

historic country
[edit](#)

County Kerry [edit](#)

0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

location
[edit](#)

Dunmore Head [edit](#)

0 references [+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

CIIC 178 in Wikidata (Q126503090)

coordinate location

52°0'36.9148"N, 10°28'23.4584"W

location	ex situ
sourcing circumstances	on-site survey
determination method or standard	on-site survey
subject has role	exhibition in the wild
stated in	OpenStreetMap

► 1 reference

52°0'36.9148"N, 10°28'23.4584"W

determination method or standard	georeferencing
object of statement has role	book entry (Ogham)
subject has role	archaeological site
stated in	academic journal article
location	ancient location

▼ 0 references

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126503090>

heritage designation

national monument of Ireland

▼ 0 references

inscription

ERC MAQI MAQI-ERICIAS MU DOVINIA (Latin)

► 1 reference

partially coincident with

CIIC 178 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)

▼ 0 references

COLUME/1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP)

▼ 0 references

178. Courmeenole (Ogham Stone Concept by the Ogham in 3D Project)

▼ 0 references

Commons category

Ogham stones in County Kerry

▼ 0 references

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KE052-059002-

▼ 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID

5145413640

▼ 0 references

Wiki Loves Monuments ID

IE-KY-0138

▼ 0 references

CIIC 178 in Wikidata (Q126503090)

Federating Ogham Stones

... using distributed data stores

CIIC 81

- **UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4**
- **OSM Node: 11071361392**
- **Wikidata: Q130529871**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthierygo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]JSSITT[A]O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	 Archaeological Site
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529871
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://wikibase.semantic-kompakt.de/entity/Q1247
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q1000294
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/56702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheragh Ringfort

Rath called
Lisheenagreine
ca. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Past: CIIC 81 at the original? findspot in Garranes (Lisheenagreine)

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level

Low

certainty description

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map

of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches". CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.!

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level

High

certainty description

on-site survey at exhibition area

method used

on-site survey

acting person

Florian Thiery

source type (detail)

on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic)

on-site survey (source type)

method description

on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision

±0.0001°

location type

Exhibition Site

point type

Exhibition

▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

method used

Georeferencing

acting person

Florian Thiery

source type (generic)

Textual Description

source type (detail)

Paper

method description

found in old documents

precision

±0.0001°

location type

Findspot

point type

Location of a Place as a Concept

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

Use each LOD/ Wikibase-Instance for data it is “famous” for

- *Linked Open Ogham Data*: providing the primary URI
 - <https://t1p.de/3xqti>
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase*: coordinates and how they are created
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata*: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase*: 3D Model & Annotations
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians*: Inscription & Persons & Words
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)

The Idea: Create LOD and feed domain-specific Wikibase Instances

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper Filter

object of representation file view wikidata id

<https://t1p.de/6pmdd>

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```

1 result in 513 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between **Semantic Kompakkt** & **Wikidata**

Federating between *Wikidata* (external IDs), *FactGrid* (related people and inscriptions), and *fuzzy-sl* (coordinates)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL


```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fsldw: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wikiq ?factgridq ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wikiq wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wikiq = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wikiq rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wikiq wdt:P8168 ?factgridq;
16   wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17   wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18   wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fg:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fsldw:Q74 fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }

```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Query results:

2 lines found 11ms in total 11ms for computation 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wikiq	?factgridq	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	caslittas	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148----	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148----	Y50000081

Jupyter Python Minions for OG(H)AM

Make cool SPARQL visualisations

Define SPARQL query service

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
?item wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
?item wdt:P189 ?site.
?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
?item wdt:P189 ?county.
?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "geo": result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None,
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites>

	item	itemLabel	geo	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892757	CIIC 206 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-9.747222 52.071944)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85395537	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892761	CIIC 207 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-9.747222 52.071944)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85395537	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892763	CIIC 208 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-9.747222 52.071944)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85395537	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892767	CIIC 209 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-9.747222 52.071944)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85395537	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892772	CIIC 210 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-9.747222 52.071944)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85395537	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
...
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
333	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry

334 rows × 7 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data with Bar Charts

```
# Define a color palette for counties
unique_counties = df['countyLabel'].unique()
county_colors = {county: color for county, color in zip(unique_counties, plt.cm.tab20.colors)}

# Group by county and site to count stones
site_counts = df.groupby(['countyLabel', 'siteLabel']).size().reset_index(name='count')

# Identify the top 2 sites per county
top_sites = site_counts.groupby('countyLabel').apply(lambda x: x.nlargest(2, 'count')).reset_index(drop=True)
```

Bar plot: the top 2 sites per county

```
# Create a bar plot for the top 3 sites per county
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
for county, group in top_sites.groupby('countyLabel'):
    plt.bar(group['siteLabel'], group['count'], color=county_colors[county], label=county)

plt.title("Top 2 Sites per County with the Most Ogham Stones")
plt.xlabel("Sites")
plt.ylabel("Number of Ogham Stones")
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
plt.legend(title="County", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Bar plot: Distribution by counties

```
# Bar plot: Distribution by counties
county_counts = df['countyLabel'].value_counts()
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
county_counts.plot(kind='bar', color=[county_colors[county] for county in county_counts.index])
plt.title("Distribution of Ogham Stones by Counties")
plt.xlabel("Counties")
plt.ylabel("Number of Ogham Stones")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Create Charts

Top 2 Sites per County with the Most Ogham Stones

- County Carlow
- County Cavan
- County Clare
- County Cork
- County Donegal
- County Galway
- County Kerry
- County Kildare
- County Kilkenny
- County Leitrim
- County Limerick
- County Louth
- County Mayo
- County Meath
- County Roscommon
- County Waterford
- County Wexford
- County Wicklow

Distribution of Ogham Stones by Counties

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q806167.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
    ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
    ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
    ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()

# Map 3: Density map with normalized values
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
  ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
  ?item rdfs:label ?label .
  ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
  ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
  ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
  ?c a oghamonto:County .
  ?c rdfs:label ?county .
  ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
  ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062	Castletimon (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.909167	-6.063611
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168	Knickeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.998056	-6.535000
193	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000045	Boleycarrigeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.947012	-6.608898
194	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000098	Donard (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	53.016944	-6.617778
195	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000040	Baltinglass (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.966389	-6.624444

196 rows x 6 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()
# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count

```
# Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count.
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
# Extract x and y coordinates from the GeoDataFrame.
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Define a scaling factor for point sizes.
size_factor = 10
sizes = gdf_mercator["count"] * size_factor

# Plot the points using a continuous colormap (e.g. 'viridis') based on the stone count.
sc = ax.scatter(x, y, s=sizes, c=gdf_mercator["count"], cmap="viridis", alpha=0.7, edgecolor="k")
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count", fontsize=16)

# Add a colour bar with label.
cbar = plt.colorbar(sc, ax=ax)
cbar.set_label("Stone Count", fontsize=12)
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

- Counties
- Cork
 - Waterford
 - Kerry
 - Kildare
 - Antrim
 - Kilkenny
 - Roscommon
 - Armagh
 - Carlow
 - Cavan
 - Clare
 - Donegal
 - Dublin
 - Fermanagh
 - Galway
 - Leitrim
 - Limerick
 - Londonderry
 - Louth
 - Mayo
 - Meath
 - Tipperary
 - Tyrone
 - Wexford
 - Wicklow

Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count

Output

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

A Linked Open Data Plugin for QGIS

The SPARQL Unicorn allows linked data queries in (Geo)SPARQL to be sent to triple stores and prepares the results for the geocommunity in QGIS.

The SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

The plugin currently offers
three main functions:

- (A) Simplified querying of
Semantic Web data sources
- (B) Transformation of QGIS
vector layers to RDF
- (C) RDF HTML-Documentation

The Unicorn's Functions

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhefter Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kin region (KinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite**
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sfMultiPolygon
- sfPoint
- sfPolygon
- wgs84_posSpatialThing

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: /rest/xyz/xyz/ (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Example queries: [Please select]

Press CTRL + S (repositories to autocomplete)

Items: Response: 196 results

Item	label	geo	county	count
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001a	Ballybrock (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.07111 52.02644)"	"Cork"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001b	Cumshingaig (Ogham Site)	"POINT(7.44856 52.14856)"	"Waterford"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001c	Bullinbeggar (Ogham Site)	"POINT(10.05111 52.27272)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001d	Killeshale East / Killeshale (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.74222 52.07044)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001e	Knockbay (Ogham Site)	"POINT(7.6 52.11389)"	"Waterford"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001f	Bullinawing (Ogham Site)	"POINT(10.34611 52.27611)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001g	Coolumagar (Ogham Site)	"POINT(9.64278 52.06111)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001h	Colbstown / Killeen Cormac (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.75639 52.05111)"	"Kildare"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001i	Ballyhank (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.60833 51.83611)"	"Cork"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001j	Knockanawee (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.79472 51.86856)"	"Cork"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001k	Whitefield (Ogham Site)	"POINT(9.70556 52.08556)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001l	Kilgrovan (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.24972 52.09556)"	"Waterford"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001m	Monatagarr (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.77944 51.97444)"	"Cork"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001n	Rockfield / Laham (Ogham Site)	"POINT(9.63667 52.12889)"	"Kerry"	1
http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001o	Rooves More (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.78467 51.88667)"	"Cork"	1

Language for query results: Engl

Layer hinzufügen

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

N4O KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?geo ?label WHERE {
2   ?item rdfs:label ?label .
3   ?item <http://ontology.ogham.link/within> <http://lod.ogham.link/data/GSD3000003> .
4   ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
5   ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
6 }
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (11) FeatureCollections Geo

- Barony
- Location
- Place
- gsp:Feature
- ns1:Barony
- ns1:GeographicLocation
- ns1:Island
- ns1:OghamSite
- ns1:Province
- sf:MultiPolygon
- sf:Point

Ogham Stones in the Province Munster

Ogham Stones in the Province Munster

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheffer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Item+Label Layer Name: holy_wells

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q126443332.
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
8 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname: Layer hinzufügen

WIKIDATA <https://w.wiki/BD2C>

Informationen Projekt - QGIS

Projekt Bearbeiten Ansicht Layer Einstellungen Eigenschaften Vektor Editor Datenbank Web Netz Vererbung Hilfe

Antarctic field camp (wd:Q4771007)
Antarctic research station (wd:Q749622)

Browser

- Google Terrain
- Google Terrain Hybrid
- Mapbox Global Terrain
- Open Weather Map Clouds
- Open Weather Map Temperature
- Open Weather Map Wind Speed
- OpenStreetMap
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.
- OpenStreetMap Monochrome
- OpenStreetMap Standard
- OpenTopoMap
- Stamen Terrain
- Stamen Toner
- Stamen Toner Light

Layer

- unicorn.holy_wells
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.

Suchwörter (Strg+W) koordinat: 41.666 70.78567 Maßstab: 1:1257452 Vergrößerung: 100% Drehung: 0,0° Zeichen: EPSG:3857

Wikidata Queries in QGIS - Holy Wells

CIIC 178

- Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head
- OSM: node/5145413640
- Wikidata: Q70892682
- O3d: 178._Coumeenole
- SMR: KE052-059002-

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 178 (5145413640)

Version #8

added historic site #NationalMonuments

Bearbeitet vor .weniger.als.einer.Minute von fthierygo

Änderungssatz #133566233

Standort: 52,1102476, -10,4731913

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	ERC MAQI MAQI- ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
moved	no
name	CIIC 178
project	ogham.link
ref:ismr	KE052-059002-
source	survey
wikidata	Q70892682
wikimedia_commons	File:Coumeenolele_O gham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

↑ Ogham in 3D Project, DIAS,
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

CIIC 178 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)^{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y10000088>

The CIIC 178 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Go Download Options: Format:

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	OS40000083 (fslid:OS40000083)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q70892682 (wde:Q70892682) [x]
shows (oghamonto:shows)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">OW13 (fslid:OW13)OW18 (fslid:OW18)OW52 (fslid:OW52)OW6 (fslid:OW6)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [x]OghamStone_Ciic (oghamonto:OghamStone_Ciic) [x]Resource (lqip:Resource) [x]Resource (Resource) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (rdf:langString) (fso6391:en)
label (rdfs:label)	CIIC 178 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (rdf:langString) (fso6391:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	178 (xsd:string)
creator (terms:creator)	0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]
license (terms:license)	deed.de (deed.de) [x]
rightsHolder (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]0000-0003-4696-2101 (0000-0003-4696-2101) [x]
inDataset (void:inDataset)	Linked_Open_Ogham (fslid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [1367 oghamonto:shows]
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStonesCIIC (fslid:PythonStonesCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones.csv (og_stones.csv) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	Y10000088_activity (fslid:Y10000088_activity)

CIIC 187

- **Kilmalkedar Church (Cill Maoilchheadair)**
- **OSM: node/9110402648**
- **Wikidata: Q70892706**
- **O3d: 187._Kilmalkedar**
- **SMR: KE052-059002-**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 187
(9110402648)

Version #5

small fixes

Bearbeitet vor 20 Tagen von fthiergeo
Änderungssatz #125625590
Standort: 52.1847478, -10.3364628

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
image	https://www.flickr.com/photos/196367420@N05/52324823400/rn/album-72177720301745883/
inscription	ANM MAILE-INBIR MACI BROCANN
name	CIIC 187
project	ogham.link
source	https://hollywells.corkkerry.com/2019/08/21/two-wells-a-whole-lot-more-at-cill-mhaoilchheadair/survey
wikidata	Q70892706

↑ Ogham in 3D Project, DIAS,
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

CIIC 187 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)^{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y10000098>

The CIIC 187 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Go **Download Options:** Format:

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
<code>disclosedAt</code> (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	OS40000162 (fslid:OS40000162)
<code>exactMatch</code> (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q70892706 (wde:Q70892706) [x]
<code>shows</code> (oghamonto:shows)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <code>OW1</code> (fslid:OW1)• <code>OW41</code> (fslid:OW41)• <code>OW6</code> (fslid:OW6)• <code>OW62</code> (fslid:OW62)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <code>OghamStone</code> (oghamonto:OghamStone) [x]• <code>OghamStone_CIIC</code> (oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC) [x]• <code>Resource</code> (rdf:Resource) [x]• <code>Resource</code> (Resource) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	CIIC 187 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
<code>identifier</code> (dce:identifier)	187 (xsd:string)
<code>creator</code> (terms:creator)	0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]
<code>license</code> (terms:license)	deed.de (deed.de) [x]
<code>rightsHolder</code> (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]• 0000-0003-4696-2101 (0000-0003-4696-2101) [x]
<code>inDataset</code> (void:inDataset)	Linked_Open_Ogham (fslid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [1867 oghamonto:shows]
<code>wasAttributedTo</code> (prov:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStonesCIIC (fslid:PythonStonesCIIC)
<code>wasDerivedFrom</code> (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones.csv (og_stones.csv) [x]
<code>wasGeneratedBy</code> (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	Y10000098_activity (fslid:Y10000098_activity)

CIIC 187 as HTML Page

Go raibh maith agat! Thx!

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